

Nox: A Hypothetical Y-type Brown Dwarf-Companion to the Sun

Rehana Kousar

A/P Chemistry Girls PGC Plandri, Azad Kashmir, Pakistan

Email: rk2389500@gmail.com

[ORCID:0000000196641686](https://orcid.org/0000000196641686)

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Abstract:

Recent astronomical discoveries have revealed methane emissions on cold brown dwarfs, mirroring the atmospheric chemistry of gas giant planets. These findings challenge traditional star formation theories and the limits of stellar mass. Using the James Webb Space Telescope, NASA identified the smallest free-floating brown dwarf, further pushing boundaries in our understanding of star formation. Observations of auroral phenomena on isolated brown dwarfs highlight complex atmospheric dynamics influenced by internal processes rather than external stellar radiation. Studies of systems like TOI-5610b provide insights into planetary and substellar formation around smaller stars, paralleling the processes observed in sun-like stars. The detection of methane in the coldest brown dwarfs expands our knowledge of substellar atmospheric chemistry, offering comparisons with planetary atmospheres. Advanced observational techniques reveal intricate atmospheric structures and weather patterns in brown dwarfs, similar to those seen on giant exoplanets. Using instruments like Gaia and Gravity, precise observations refine models of stellar and substellar formation, revealing unexpected temperature inversions in brown dwarf atmospheres, typically associated with planets under external heating. The concept of our Solar System as a binary star system offers a fascinating avenue for theoretical exploration. This study explores a hypothetical scenario where our Sun hosts Nox, a Y-type brown dwarf located 800 AU away, reshaping Solar System dynamics and deepening our understanding of binary star systems.

Keywords: Brown dwarfs, Y-type, companion star, Solar System dynamics, astronomical observations

1. Introduction

Astronomers have detected methane emissions on a cold brown dwarf, indicating complex atmospheric chemistry similar to that of gas giant planets. This finding aids in understanding the atmospheric processes of both brown dwarfs and exoplanet [1]. Using NASA's James Webb Space

Telescope, researchers identified the tiniest free-floating brown dwarf with only three to four times the mass of Jupiter. This discovery challenges our understanding of star formation and the lower mass limit of star-like objects [2]. The James Webb Space Telescope observed an auroral phenomenon on a brown dwarf without a companion star. This finding reveals complex atmospheric dynamics that might be influenced by internal processes rather than external stellar radiation [3]. A study of the brown dwarf TOI-5610b around an M dwarf using the TESS and ground-based radial velocity data has provided insights into the properties and dynamics of such systems, contributing to our understanding of planet and brown dwarf formation around smaller stars [4]. New observations suggest that the formation of brown dwarfs follows a process similar to that of sun-like stars. This supports the idea that brown dwarfs are a natural byproduct of star formation processes, differing mainly by their inability to sustain hydrogen fusion [5]. Researchers detected methane in the atmosphere of the coldest known brown dwarfs. This discovery enhances our understanding of chemical processes in substellar atmospheres and their comparison to planetary atmospheres [6]. Astronomers have developed a technique to capture detailed structures of brown dwarf atmospheres, revealing their complex cloud layers and weather patterns. This has implications for understanding the atmospheres of giant exoplanets [7]. Using the Gaia and Gravity instruments, astronomers have detected brown dwarfs in close proximity to bright stars. This helps refine models of stellar and substellar formation and improves detection techniques for faint objects near bright sources [8]. Observations from 2024 provide new insights into the birth of brown dwarfs, showing similarities with the star formation process. This study helps in distinguishing between the various pathways leading to the formation of substellar objects [9]. A study on brown dwarf atmospheres revealed unexpected temperature inversions, where the upper atmosphere is warmer than the lower layers. This phenomenon is usually associated with planets having external heat sources, making this discovery particularly intriguing for brown dwarfs without such influences [10].

1.1 Types of Brown Dwarf

Brown dwarfs are substellar objects that occupy the mass range between the heaviest gas giant planets and the lightest stars. They are not massive enough to sustain hydrogen fusion reactions in their cores, which is the defining characteristic of true stars. Brown dwarfs are classified based on their spectral types, which primarily reflect their temperatures. Here are the main types:

1.1.1 L-type (L Dwarfs):

- **Temperature Range:**
Approximately 1,300 to 2,200 K.
- **Characteristics:** L dwarfs are cooler than M dwarfs and exhibit prominent metal hydride and alkali metal lines in their spectra. They often show reddish colors due to the presence

of clouds of iron and silicate dust, as well as molecules like water (H₂O) and methane (CH₄) in their atmospheres.

1.1.2 T-type Brown Dwarfs (T Dwarfs):

- **Temperature Range:**
Approximately 500 to 1,400 K.
- **Characteristics:** T dwarfs are cooler than L dwarfs and exhibit blue to greenish colors. Their spectra are dominated by strong methane absorption features, especially in the near-infrared. Unlike L dwarfs, the clouds in T dwarfs settle below the visible atmosphere, resulting in clearer spectra with less dust.

1.1.3 Y-type (Y Dwarfs)

- **Temperature Range:** Below 500 K.
- **Characteristics:** Y dwarfs are the coolest type of brown dwarfs, with temperatures similar to that of the human body. Their spectra exhibit absorption features from ammonia (NH₃) and water (H₂O), and they have very low luminosities. These brown dwarfs have spectra dominated by molecules found in cool, dense environments. Their exact spectral characteristics are still being studied, as they are relatively new discoveries. Y dwarfs are often found to be close to the temperature range of planets.[11][12][13][14]

Each type of brown dwarf represents a different stage in the cooling and aging process of these substellar objects. As brown dwarfs cool over time, they transition from one spectral type to another, moving from L to T to Y types.

1.2 The Companion Star: Nox

Imagine a scenario where our familiar Solar System is not as solitary as it seems. In this hypothetical exploration, we delve into the intriguing possibility of a binary star system where our Sun is accompanied by a Y-type brown dwarf named Nox, orbiting at a distance of 800 astronomical units (AU) from the Sun. This speculative system offers a unique glimpse into how such a configuration could impact our cosmic neighborhood.

Nox is a Y-type brown dwarf, a type of substellar object that lacks sufficient mass to sustain hydrogen fusion like a main-sequence star but is more massive than gas giant planets. Y-type brown dwarfs are known for their relatively cool temperatures and dim luminosities, making them challenging to detect in the visible spectrum but prominent in infrared observations.

1.2.1 Orbital Dynamics and Parameters

- **Orbital Distance:** Nox orbits our Sun at a distance of 800 AU. This vast distance places it far beyond the known planets and extends into the outer reaches of the Solar System.
- **Orbital Characteristics:** Nox follows an elliptical orbit around the Sun, with a highly elongated path due to its large orbital distance. The eccentricity of Nox's orbit could lead to significant gravitational interactions with distant Kuiper Belt objects and the hypothetical Oort Cloud.
- **Influence on Solar System Dynamics:** The presence of Nox would introduce gravitational perturbations that could affect the orbits of distant objects in the Solar System. It might contribute to the shaping of the Kuiper Belt and Oort Cloud dynamics, influencing the periodic comet showers that occasionally visit the inner Solar System.

1.3 Characteristics and Impact on Earth

- **Visibility and Influence:** Nox would appear as a faint point of light in the sky, possibly detectable with advanced telescopes and infrared sensors. Its presence would not significantly affect the overall brightness of daylight on Earth due to its dim luminosity.
- **Climate and Habitability:** The gravitational influence of Nox, even at 800 AU, could potentially induce slight variations in Earth's orbit over long timescales. These variations might lead to subtle changes in climate patterns, although the effect would be minimal compared to more proximate astronomical phenomena.
- **Geological Activity:** The gravitational tug from Nox might contribute to minor variations in Earth's tides and could theoretically influence geological processes, such as seismic activity and volcanic eruptions, although these effects would likely be negligible.

1.4 Formation and Evolutionary Scenarios

- **Formation:** Nox could have formed alongside our Sun from the same molecular cloud, or it might have been captured later in the Solar System's history through a gravitational interaction with passing stars or interstellar clouds.
- **Stability and Longevity:** The stability of such a binary system would depend on the orbital dynamics and the relative masses of the Sun and Nox. Over millions to billions of years, gravitational interactions could alter the orbits of planets and other objects, potentially leading to orbital resonances and interactions.

1.4 Parameters of the Hypothetical Companion Star (Nox)

In this hypothetical scenario, our Sun is accompanied by a brown dwarf star of Y-type, named Nox, orbiting at a distance of 800 astronomical units (AU) from the Sun.

Orbital Parameters

- **Distance and Semi-Major Axis (a):**

- Distance from the Sun to Nox (r): $r=800$ AU
- The semi-major axis (a) of the orbit is half the distance between perihelion and aphelion:
- $a=r/2=800/2=400$ AU

- **Eccentricity (e):**

- Eccentricity describes the shape of the orbit. For simplicity, let's assume a moderate eccentricity:
- $e= 0.5$
- This value suggests that Nox's orbit is somewhat elongated, but not extremely eccentric.

- **Orbital Period (T):**

The orbital period of Nox around the Sun can be estimated using Kepler's third law:

$$T^2=4\pi^2a^3/G(M_{\odot}+M_{Nox})$$

Fig.1 2D Model of the Solar System and a Brown Dwarf- a Companion Star of our Sun

where:

- T is the orbital period,
- a is the semi-major axis,
- G is the gravitational constant ($6.67430 \times 10^{-11} \text{ m}^3 \text{ kg}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-2}$)
- $M_{\odot}$ is the mass of the Sun ($1.989 \times 10^{30} \text{ kg}$),
- M_{Nox} is the mass of Nox
- (hypothetically estimated).

Assuming a rough estimate for M_{Nox} (since actual Y-type brown dwarfs vary widely in mass), let's say $M_{\text{Nox}} = 0.05M_{\odot}$ (approximately 10% of the Sun's mass):

$$T^2 = 4\pi^2(400 \text{ AU})^3 / G \cdot (1.05M_{\odot})$$

Calculating T

$$T = [4\pi^2(400 \text{ AU})^3 / G \cdot (1.05M_{\odot})]^{1/2}$$

$$T \approx 4255 \text{ years}$$

Therefore, Nox would have an orbital period around the Sun of approximately 4255 years.

The orbital period of Sedna around the Sun is approximately 11,400 years. This extremely long period is due to Sedna's highly elliptical orbit, which takes it from its perihelion distance of about 76 astronomical units (AU) to its aphelion distance of about 936 AU, making it one of the most distant known objects in the Solar System.

In our hypothetical model of our solar system, the eccentricity of Sedna orbital and other KBOs is due to the presence of Brown Dwarf at a distance of 800 AU or closer to or further away from our sun(see figure.1).

1.5 General Mathematical Calculations for Y-Type Brown Dwarf Companion Star

1. Orbital Parameters:

Assuming a circular orbit for simplicity:

Orbital Radius (a): Distance between the brown dwarf and the Sun

a=semi-major axis

Orbital Period (T): Time taken for one complete orbit Kepler's third law gives us:

$$T^2 = 4\pi^2 a^3 / G(M_{\odot} + M_{\text{BD}})$$

Where:

- T is in years,
- a is in astronomical units (AU),
- G is the gravitational constant.

2. **Surface Temperature (T_{surface}):**

The effective temperature of a Y-type brown dwarf can range from about 300 K to 500 K, depending on its mass and age.

3. **Luminosity (L):**

The luminosity of a brown dwarf can be estimated using:

$$L \propto R^2 T_{\text{sur}}^4$$

Where R is the radius of the brown dwarf.

These calculations would require specific values and other parameters to provide precise numerical results. The equations above provide a framework for exploring the characteristics and dynamics of a Y-type brown dwarf companion in a binary star system scenario.

1.6 Conclusion

This hypothetical binary star system underscores the dynamic nature of stellar interactions and planetary evolution. While our current understanding of the Solar System reveals a single star dominance, exploring scenarios with a brown dwarf companion offers valuable insights into the diversity and complexity of star systems throughout the universe. Such speculations stimulate further inquiry into the formation and evolution of planetary systems, pushing the boundaries of our understanding of celestial dynamics and the potential for habitability beyond our own cosmic neighborhood.

1.7 Conflicts of Interest

The author declares no conflicts of interest regarding the publication of this paper.

1.8 Declaration of ChatGPT

As English is not my first language and I am not an English language expert, I used an AI language model to rewrite my article and made corrections during proofreading. I also declare that all concepts are my own original ideas.

1.9 Data Availability Statement:

No Data associated in the manuscript.

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